

The Diabetic Tsunami in Karnataka: A Cross-sectional Study**Hema Divakar¹, Hrishikesh Pai², Sheetal Joshi³, Rita Singh⁴, Poorni Narayanan⁵,
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Abstract:**Background:** Karnataka ranks as the 9th most populous state in India and the second-most populous state in South India. This study aims to evaluate the undiagnosed cases of prediabetes and diabetes in Karnataka, specifically analyzing the most frequent age groups.**Method:** The cross-sectional study conducted from June 2023 to May 2024 collected data at screening camps held in both urban and rural areas of Karnataka. Participants aged 13 to 95 years who visited designated data collection centers and had their blood glucose levels assessed were included if they had not been previously diagnosed with diabetes.**Results:** A total of 2806 individuals from Karnataka were screened, categorized into the following age groups: 13-19 years (n=26), 20-39 years (n=1259), 40-64 years (n=1188), 65-79 years (n=309), and 80-95 years (n=24). Within this cohort, 30.18% (n=847) were diagnosed with diabetes and 36.21% (n=1016) with prediabetes. Prediabetes was most common in the 20-39 age group (57.58%), while diabetes was highest in the 40-64 age group (54.07%).**Conclusion:** The study highlights alarming rates of diabetes and prediabetes in Karnataka, emphasizing the need for urgent public health interventions. Future efforts should focus on enhancing healthcare infrastructure, promoting healthy lifestyles, and increasing diabetes awareness to mitigate the growing burden of diabetes in India.**Keywords:** Diabetes, Prediabetes, Policies, Healthcare, India, Karnataka.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a chronic metabolic disorder marked by eminent blood sugar levels occurring from compromised insulin emission or resistance [1]. It accounts for 1.6 million cases within the NCD burden [2] In 2021, approximately 74.2 million adults between 20 and 79 years were living with diabetes as reported by the International Diabetes Federation [3]. Studies indicate that there is a chance that the number accelerates to 134 million by 2045 [4].

As a non-communicable disease (NCD), its onset is typically gradual, necessitating long-term management [2]. Among the primary risk factors and contributors to the rising prevalence of diabetes, particularly type-2 diabetes (T2D), includes high body mass index (BMI) and sedentary lifestyles. The Global Burden of Disease study reveals that raised BMI is responsible for 41.2% of T2D-related

deaths and 54.0% of disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) in 2017 [5,6]. Diagnosing diabetes is crucial for initiating treatment, and effectively managing diabetes is essential for minimizing complications. However, there remains a significant number of undiagnosed cases [7]. Middle-income countries host approximately 177.6 million undiagnosed individuals.

Africa exhibits the highest proportion at 69.2%, followed by South-East Asia at 57.5% and the Western Pacific at 54% [8]. A 2021 study indicates that about 57% (43.9 million people) of adults in India living with diabetes are undiagnosed [4]. Karnataka ranks as the 9th most populous state in India and the second-most populous state in South India, contributing 16% to diabetic prevalence in 2010 [9,10]. However, there is a lack of recent data on undiagnosed cases. Additionally, information on

which age groups are experiencing higher incidences in Karnataka is scarce. To address this gap, this study intends to reveal the undiagnosed statistics of diabetes and prediabetes in Karnataka, specifically highlighting the higher-risk age groups.

Methods

Study Design: The study adopted a cross-sectional design to underscore the prevalence of prediabetes and diabetes in individuals aged 13 years and older. The data were gathered through screening camps conducted between June 2023 and May 2024, encompassing a variety of urban and rural settings of Karnataka including hospitals, residential areas, banks, and community clubs and health centres.

Selection Criteria: Participants aged 13-95 years from Karnataka who visited designated data collection centers, had their blood glucose levels evaluated, and were previously undiagnosed with diabetes were included in the study. Exclusions applied to non-residents of Karnataka, individuals with missing or incomplete blood glucose data, and those who did not consent.

Data Collection: Data was collected from various centers across Karnataka, including urban sites like hospitals, residential areas, banks, community clubs and health centres and health workers (ASHA Workers). Screening camps were strategically established to conduct random blood glucose checks using calibrated glucometers and determine participants' glycemic status based on established criteria, classifying them as Normal (<100 mg/dL), Prediabetic (100-125 mg/dL), or Diabetic (≥ 126 mg/dL).

Data Analysis: The data was meticulously scrutinized for consistency and completeness before being assembled and entered into the MS Excel Sheet. The dataset was presented concisely using summary statistics, such as frequencies and percentages, and the results were visually represented via graphs.

Ethical Considerations: The study was conducted in accordance with set standards and guidelines and was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee (IEC). Permission to participate in the study was sought from all the participants through verbal consent before the data collection process commenced.

Results

A total of 2806 individuals from Karnataka were screened for the study, with the majority reclining in age groups 20-39 (n=1259; 45%) and 40-64 (n=1188; 42%) (Table 1). Among the participants, 30.18% (n=847) were diagnosed with diabetes, while 36.21% (n=1016) were identified as having prediabetes.

Prediabetes prevalence was notably prominent among individuals aged 20-39 years, affecting 57.58% (n=478) of this age group. In comparison, 40.55% of individuals in the 40-64 age group (n=412) and 40.55% of those in the 65-79 age group (n=114) were recorded as having prediabetes. For diabetes, 54.07% (n=458) of individuals in the 40-64 age group were diagnosed, followed by 28.09% (n=238) among those aged 20-39 years, and 16.05% (n=136) in the 65-79 age group.

Table 1: Demographic details of Study Participants

Age Groups	N (%)
13-19 Age	26 (1)
20-39 Age	1259 (45)
40-64 Age	1188 (42)
65-79 Age	309 (11)
80-95 Age	24 (1)
Total	2806

Discussion

Our study in Karnataka revealed a concerning prevalence of diabetes, particularly among adults aged 40-64. This aligns with a study from Goa, which found higher occurrences of diabetes in the 40 to 59 years age group (18.3%) and the 60 to 79 years age group (37.2%) compared to individuals aged 20 to 39 (2%) [11].

In consistence, according to current CDC report, incidence rates of diagnosed diabetes are higher among adults aged 45 to 64 years (14.5%), and ≥ 65 (24.4%) compared to those aged 18 to 44 (3%) [12]. In a multivariable assessment, the odds of screening were 40% to 70% higher in individuals

aged ≥ 45 years [13]. These findings reaffirm that advancing age is a significant risk factor for diabetes. With advanced age, factors such as hormonal changes, malnutrition, physical inactivity, and weight gain become more frequent, contributing to the increased incidence of the disease [14,15]

In the 20-39 age group, the prevalence of prediabetes was significantly higher at 47.04%. Recent CDC reports indicated that 38% of adults aged 18 and older, roughly 97.6 million people, have prediabetes [12]. This trend is similar to the findings of Al-Zahrani et al., who reported that 33.33% of those aged 25-44 had prediabetes, and

61.67% of individuals aged 18-24, compared to just 5% in older adults [16].

Figure 1: Undiagnosed Diabetes and Prediabetes across various age groups

Between 2001 and 2010, the prevalence of diabetes among individuals aged 20-39 remained stable. However, there was a significant increase in diabetes cases among those aged 30-39 between 2016 and 2017 [17]. These studies, along with our findings, suggest that diabetes is becoming more common among young and middle-aged individuals, emphasizing the critical importance of early intervention and public health strategies to mitigate future health impacts. In 2010, Karnataka reported a diabetic prevalence of 16% [10]. According to a current report, the incidence of new cases has risen significantly, with diabetes now at 30.18% and prediabetes at 36.21%, nearly doubling the previous figures.

Similarly, in Chennai, diabetes prevalence among adults increased from 11.6% in 1995 to 18.6% in 2006 [18]. The most prominent reason for this increase is the rise in sedentary lifestyles in India. In 2005, six areas of India; Delhi and Ballabgarh in the north, Chennai and Trivandrum in the south, Nagpur in the west, and Dibrugarh in the east—reported overall inactivity rates of 12.6% among males and 18.9% among females. By 2014, these levels had escalated to 40.3% among males and 59.6% among females in rural areas, and to 58.7% in males and 71.2% in females in urban regions [19]. Urbanization has significantly increased T2D rates, primarily due to dietary patterns characterized by high carbohydrate consumption and higher consumption of processed and calorie-dense foods [20, 21]. Other factors that may contribute to diabetes include, stress, obesity, tobacco use, and increasing life expectancy [22].

Diabetes imposes a substantial economic burden on Indian households, driven by high healthcare costs, productivity losses, and diminished quality of life. The disease contributes significantly to India's health burden, with Karnataka alone recording a DALY rate of 25,790 per 100,000 individuals affected by NCD, including diabetes, accounting for about 2.4% of the nation's 4.7 million deaths [23,24]. Despite well-crafted initiatives, policy implementation in India faces substantial challenges, due to logistical constraints, such as inadequate healthcare infrastructure and uneven distribution of specialized care facilities [25,26]. Targeted strategies are crucial to prevent the progression from prediabetes to diabetes, particularly among younger adults. Improving rural healthcare infrastructure is crucial for diabetes prevention and management, ensuring adequate screening and treatment facilities [27]. Initiatives such as community-based screenings, mobile health units, and public education campaigns are pivotal for early detection and raising awareness about diabetes risk factors and healthy lifestyles [28,29]. Addressing these challenges requires integrated public health initiatives and robust policy frameworks to effectively reduce the burden of diabetes in India.

Conclusion

This study reveals a significant number of incidences of prediabetes among young adults and diabetes among middle-aged adults, underscoring the urgent need to address the escalating diabetes crisis in India, particularly in Karnataka. Urgent public health interventions are essential, focusing

on enhancing healthcare infrastructure, promoting healthy behaviors, and increasing diabetes awareness. These efforts must adapt to the evolving trends of diabetes increase, ensuring proactive measures to mitigate the growing burden effectively.

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